

Quest for a New Paradigm in Researches in Philosophy of Education in India in the Postmodern Era

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ABSTRACT : According some surveys of the educational research in India, philosophy of education appears to be a neglected area both in terms of quality and quantity. In this paper an attempt has been made to trace out the causes of such a depressing state of affairs that characterized research studies in philosophy of education and provide with a schema that may make necessary keyhole through which researcher in the field of philosophy of education can peer in and experience successful engagement of ideas analyzed in a new way.

Keywords : Philosophy of education, Postmodern era, Mechanics of concept analysis.

Prelude: A Western Episode :

Philosophy of education in the U.S.A. in the first half of the last century was an important and independent genre in the study of foundations of education (Slattery, 2006) and it enjoyed periods of respect and perhaps of notoriety (Schubert, 1986), particularly in the time of John Dewey (1859-1952) who was both philosopher and educationist. But, unfortunately, by the early 1960s, the theoretical split between philosophy and education created much tension and suspicion within both departments: Departments of philosophy of education were dismantled and

subsumed under departments of educational leadership, administration or policy studies in many universities. While singling out the primary reasons for such 'troubled marriage' between philosophy and education, we can quote Bruce Wileshire (of Rutgers University), whose words should be taken as a challenge rather than an insult on the teachers of education: -

“Educators in Universities seldom talk about education. Administrators talk about administrative problems, professors talk about problems in their special field of study, and those who talk about education,

professors in education departments, are generally despised and shunned. Besides, even if one does listen to this latter group, one usually hears education talked about as if it were just another special field of study, not as something that vitally concerns us all just because we are human” (Wilshire, 1990 P.21)

Another reason responsible for the theoretical split between philosophy and education in U.S.A. was, as Eisner wrote, “Philosophy is nagging, it cajoles students into asking questions about basic assumptions, it generates doubts and uncertainties, and it is said, it keeps people from getting their work done” (Eisner, 1991. P.4) and thus for the time being, philosophy was being regarded as an academic distraction in programmes preparing researches in social sciences. But, amazingly, more the field of philosophy of education suffered a cataclysmic contraction – more the field, that somehow survived, had become an academic, intellectual field, worthy of name (Pinar, 2004).

Thus, even after the passing away of John Dewey, philosophy of education continued to exist as either an elective paper or a short unit of study in foundation courses (philosophical/ Psychological/ sociological foundations of education etc.) in most undergraduate and postgraduate degree programmes and in the English speaking world, and the field began to be enriched by a variety of invaluable contributions in the wake of the emergence of the analytical movement, instigated by Russell, Wittgenstein and others (Seshadri, 1991).

The Indian case:

To start with the Indian experiences of research in philosophy of education, the most

reliable literatures, which for us are easily accessible and with which we have been able to become familiar, are the surveys of educational research, published by the NCERT and in almost all the survey reports, we may give a large attention to one writer, namely C. Seshadri, mainly because his observations perfectly suit the purpose of this paper.

As Seshadri has observed, “at one time, philosophy of education enjoyed the status of a subject of study in its own right in teacher preparatory programmes....When the educational theory package in teacher education programmes came under review from the point of view of relevance it was thought that an interdisciplinary course which combined functional segments from the foundational disciplines would meet the needs of the students better. The result of this approach to de-emphasize educational theory per se was that, philosophy of education as an intellectual discipline lost its place...” (Seshadri, 2006, p.1). And this ‘low market value’ of philosophy of education in post-independent India seems to have affected the researches in this field too.

In the fourth survey of educational research, Seshadri had lamented the depressing state of affairs that characterized research studies in philosophy of education, such as a highly restricted paradigm with ‘study of educational philosophy/ ideas/ contributions of.....’ types of researches virtually defining the domain of the field; lack of methodological rigour; philosophical indifference to ongoing educational happenings; an almost pathological obsession with the past and absence of enterprise to explore the new or ‘here and now’. After a lapse of five years, in the fifth survey he (Seshadri) felt dismayed that not only had there been no visible improvement

in the overall situation but also that the quality of the output during the intervening years had deteriorated further.

An appraisal of the crisis:

Firstly, the major trend of philosophical inquiry into educational field has not gone beyond looking upon philosophy of education as the study of 'isms' and 'their educational implications'. Hence, when such inquiry comes to actual curriculum transaction, things become more difficult due to the researchers' not possessing sufficient requisite acquaintance with the methods of philosophical inquiry and logic. As a result of which, all miscellaneous, undifferentiated discourses on educational aims, content and methodology get peddled as philosophy of education (Seshadri, 1991).

Secondly, In the fourth survey of research in education, M.B. Buch commented, "The philosophy of education thus appears to be a rather neglected area of study.....The obvious reason for this is that this area demands a deeper level of thinking and clarity in articulation of one's idea – which is not that easy – than any other areas that demands more on empirical data and their interpretation" (Buch, 1991, P.15).

Thirdly, the widespread philosophical activity in India that prevailed before the advent of colonialism, subsequently showed substantial decline (Raghuramraju, 2006) and at this backdrop, this need not come as a surprise that researches in philosophy of education have not emerged as a vibrant, intellectual activity. To be more specific in the language of Professor Kalidas Bhattacharyay, the proud son of Professor K. C. Bhattacharyay, "traditional Indian philosophy is the corpus of philosophical doctrines and dissertations that have been

current in India for at least two millenniums and communicated from generation to generationThe beauty of the whole tradition that it was a perfectly living widespread study among Indian philosophers till only the other day – till, one may say, a hundred and twenty years back....This was the case even during the whole period of Muslim rule in India" (Bhattacharyay, K, 1982, P. 171-2).

Fourthly (this point, to me, is the most important one as may be inferred from the previous point), colonialism did bring about certain major structural changes in the practice of philosophy in India which certainly played havoc with the field of philosophy of education. Let us take note of the historical narration of Swami Vivekananda, "...at the end of the Mohammedan period...an entirely new power made its appearance on the arena and slowly began to assert its prowess in the affairs of the Indian world...(this power) ...is very new, its nature and working are so foreign to Indian mind, its rise so inconceivable, and its vigour so insuperable that though it wields the suzerain power till now, only a handful of Indians understand what this power is" (Swami Vivekananda, 1994, P.448).

As a result of the appearance of this new power, such philosophical activity with debates at its centre, widespread in India during classical times, has since faded away (Raghuramraju, 2006) and moreover, "most of the others who have done philosophy in India since have more or less accepted western philosophy, and that too as it was understood by the British thinkers, and granted recognition to that much only of Indianism which was intelligible, in terms of western ideas. The rest was rejected as

dogmatic, magical, tribal, romantic, speculative and what not?" (Bhattacharyay, 1982, P. 173).

Keeping this context in mind, let us now go back to our inquiry into the present state of research in the philosophy of education in India. Among the researches conducted, "more popular, however, are researches which have adopted the framework of western philosophical schools like Pragmatism, Existentialism or Idealism. These researches have attempted to understand the educational thought of Indian educationists and Indian educational systems with the help of" (Seshadri, 1991) western philosophical theories stated above. But, to have real 'Swaraj in Ideas', it would be interesting to explore these very educational themes and systems from the point of view of Indian philosophical thinking, i.e. to turn the Indian search light of philosophical inquiry upon the western 'isms' and 'systems'. But, unfortunately, "this has not been attempted in sufficient measure." (Seshadri, 1991).

Lastly, it is an unfortunate situation that "there has been very little communication between philosophers and educationists.... The absence of interest on the part of philosophers in the problems of education appears odd, considering the vitality of current educational debate in the wake of recent developments like the announcement of a new National Policy of education, the appointment of National Commissions on teachers, to cite only a few. Again, discussions currently going on about value orientation of education, university autonomy and academic freedom, and such other issues have not involved philosophers to the extent one would wish" (Seshadri, 1993, P.53). This being the reality, the researches in philosophy of education had to come under fire.

Quest for Schema:

We must remember that it is not possible to take note of all aspects of the crisis under this study and the number of possible explanatory solutions that could be pondered over is virtually limitless. However, we may try here to provide with a schema that may make necessary keyhole through which researcher in the field of philosophy of education can peer in and experience successful engagement of ideas analyzed in a new way.

First, historically, philosophy has expressed itself, we may say, in three modes – namely speculative, normative and critical or analytical.

Speculative plane concerns itself with general inquiries into what lies beyond this phenomenal existence – may it be God, spirit and so on.

Normative philosophy deals with the ethical dimensions of human affairs, whereas, critical or analytical philosophy concerns itself with concepts, theories, arguments and conceive its task as one of understanding and illuminating the syntax of language and discourses.

Now, to equate researches in philosophy of education with anyone of the above-mentioned mode in a rigid manner would seem dogmatic and biased; Hence, is needed a comprehensive view of philosophy of education which would indicate a wide range of research problems and issues than mere study of an educational thinker or system in a general holistic way (Seshadri, 1991).

In the fourth survey, Seshadri has hopefully made an attempt to show that a researcher in philosophy of education can make explicit the mechanics of concept analysis with different aspects of education.

The mechanics of concept analysis

Aspect	Task
<p>I. Elucidation of concepts</p>	<p>Isolating the conceptual from fact, value, moral opinion. Examination of the meanings of words with reference to vagueness, ambiguity, emotive overtones.</p> <p>Formulation of defining characteristics of the concept by identifying the logically necessary conditions to the extent possible by –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supplying the context, - appealing to the standard example - searching for the paradigm case, and - searching for counter examples, contrary cases. <p>Mapping the boundaries of the concept by –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - creation of imaginative cases - invented cases - suppositious cases, and - counter-factual instances
<p>II. Appraisal of educational Statements and arguments</p>	<p>Study of the logical grammar of the sentence to determine their logical status. Whether they assert propositions or are imperatives, value judgments or emotive expressions).</p> <p>Analysis of educational slogans and metaphors, appraisal of educational arguments and resolution of controversies – identifying the point(s) of the controversies, checking for conceptual confusion, fallacies of reasoning, formal validity of inferences.</p>
<p>III. Justification of educational prescriptions & preferences</p>	<p>Justification in term of values, appeal to reason, formal requirements of consistency.</p>
<p>IV. Validation of educational Theories.</p>	<p>Elucidation of concepts involved. Examination of the assumptions of the Theory. Are they sound? Are testable or metaphysical? Are they morally acceptable?</p> <p>Justification of perspective conclusions of the theory in terms of the assumptions, consistency of arguments, internal coherence of prescriptions. (Seshadri, 1991, P.51-2)</p>

There is no denying that this mechanics of concept analysis, proposed by C. Seshadri, is just a rough sketch of how we can proceed with a rigorous methodology in the field the philosophical inquiry, and there are still many more ways to conceive the methodological direction. However, this 'developing mechanics of concept analysis' in philosophy of education itself can be worth researching.

Second, as researches in educational philosophy need deeper level of thinking and clarity in articulation, so language development, various linguistic skills enrichment, specially development of the skills of logical presentation are to be made inevitable.

Third, to rejuvenate researches in philosophy of education significant debates and dialogues in contemporary Indian philosophy are to be encouraged and nurtured and even educationists are to grow a genuine test for philosophical inquiry in its truest sense. "A host of areas in Indian Education", wrote Seshadri, "are crying out for philosophical enlightenment and the sooner the challenge is accepted, the better it would be for the development of clear and informed thinking on issues of educational policy and practice" (Seshadri, 1991, P.52).

With the advent of globalization, the existing philosophical theories are receding very fast. They fail to vitalize and accelerate the stream of consciousness, related to education and philosophy of education. Any discipline gets vigour through constant negotiation and modification and philosophy of education is no exception to this assumption. Hence, it has to be 'modernized in perspectives' so that it can incorporate new thoughts and new perspectives in philosophy of education.

Fourth, comes the necessity for evolving an educational framework, purely indigenous in nature but totally modern in its outlook. Prof. K. C. Bhattacharyay, the eminent philosopher of the last century, while delivering a discourse at a meeting of the students of the Hooghly College sometimes during 1928-30, proclaimed, "our education has not so far helped us to understand ourselves, to understand the significance of our past, the realities of our present and our mission of the future. It has tended to drive our real mind into the unconsciousness and to replace it by a shadow mind that has no roots in our past and in our real present.Our thought is hybrid through and through and inevitably sterile. Slavery has entered into our very soul."

For remedying such a condition, it was observed in the 'National Policy on Education' (NPE, 1986) that, "... the national curriculum framework, which contains a common core along with other components that are flexible. The common core will include the history of India's freedom movement, the constitutional obligations, and other component essential to nurture national identity". Keeping this view in due consideration, researches in philosophy of education need to be redesigned and reshaped.

And **finally**, Philosophical inquiry in the field of education is to come closer to the living reality instead of being confined to the ancient lore and needs to strengthen its links with emerging policies in Indian and global education.

Epilogue:

In recent years in the west, philosophers of education have been paying a great deal of attention to a trend within philosophy which may loosely be referred to as 'postmodernist' and

accounts of postmodernism abound today in the literature of both general philosophy and educational theory. But to define what postmodernism actually means in a specific way is next to impossible than to conceive it as a logical and ideological attack on the claim of the supremacy of universal rationality. Philosophical postmodernism is a development of which one might say that, like many other things, it has done more good than harm and it has done an awful lot of harm! (Clive, 1993) As with most philosophical movements, it is perhaps best viewed as a rich quarry in which we can go searching for gems of insight while not feeling obliged to take home all the rubble.

From 1970's onwards postmodernism as it was made popularized by none other than Michel Foucault, Jacques Derida, Edward Said and others made its influence felt in different fields of art and architecture, in the field of philosophy and social sciences. Almost since 1990's in India, much has been achieved by Ahish Nandy, Sudipta Kaviraj, Partha Chatterjee, Sudhir Kakar and others to unveil the true nature of psychology and political culture of colonialism and by Ranajit Guha and others to amazingly expound the hitherto unnoticed and unknown subaltern history of India but unfortunately not even a single work had been ushered to document or reveal hitherto unknown details of historical development in Indian education system through 'a postmodern eye.'

Against this backdrop, the inter-disciplinary approach, the multidimensional phenomenon of research in philosophy of education being the postmodern demand, it would be quite pertinent to look into the philosophical inquiry in the field of education through a 'a postmodern eye' and

vice-versa. A deeper level of understanding of the aims and objectives of the research project followed by a rigorous mechanics of concept analysis which tends to be free from ambiguity and which will be made to remain open to addition, alteration, modification and even zero audit may kindle hope in the present situation and this new paradigm in the postmodern era may restore to philosophy of education its rightful place for which we can be proud of.

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